

Prospective Study of Evaluation of Diabetic Ulcer Severity Score in Predicting Outcome in Patients with Diabetic Foot Ulcer at ESICMC & H Kalaburgi

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Abstract:

Background and Objectives: A number of foot ulcer classification systems have been devised in an attempt to categorize ulcers more effectively and allow effective comparison of the outcome of routine management. DUSS (diabetic ulcer severity score) is one of the latest wound-based system of classification which needs to be validated. Our aim was validation of the score with patient outcomes including healing and amputation.

Methods: Total of 102 diabetic patients attending surgical outpatient clinic or admitted into the hospital with foot ulcers irrespective of duration of ulcer were included in the study. Necessary data was collected. DUSS score was calculated for each patient and analysis was done using SPSS package version 23.

Results and interpretation: The mean age of the participants in the study is 58.373 years, with the highest incidence between the age groups 51 - 60 years. Among the study population, 74% were males and 26% were females. In our study there were 15 patients with DUSS Score 1, 49 with DUSS Score 2, 20 with DUSS score 3, 18 with DUSS score 4. Among DUSS Score one, all patients underwent debridement. Among DUSS Score two, 19 patients underwent debridement, 30 patients underwent Minor amputation (Rays Amputation). Among patients with DUSS score three, 15 patients underwent debridement, 4 patients underwent minor amputations (Rays / forefoot amputation) and one patient underwent major amputation (BKA/AKA). Among patients with DUSS score four, 13 patients underwent major amputations, 4 patients underwent debridement and one patient underwent minor amputation. In our Study, 27 patients were healed primarily, 13 patients underwent grafting and 44 underwent Amputations.

Conclusion: DUSS scoring system provides an easy diagnostic tool for anticipating probability of healing /amputation and need for surgery by combining four clinically assessable wound-based parameters. It can be very helpful for the stratification of study groups depending on severity of ulcers and it provides a simple, streamlined approach in a clinical setting that requires no investigative equipment although subsequent adequate wound care is an indispensable prerequisite to the DUSS being a valid diagnostic tool.

Keywords: Diabetic Ulcer Severity Score, DUSS, diabetic foot, diabetic foot ulcer.

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Introduction

Diabetes affects almost every system in the body with the foot at particularly high risk for developing complications such as recurrent infections that requires surgical procedures, interventions hospitalizations.

Diabetic foot ulcer is one of the common cause of patients getting admitted in hospitals. It accounts for major morbidity and increased mortality. Since it affects quality of life, it mostly ends up in amputation. Ulcers leads to amputations with a relative risk of greater than eight at the rate of

9.9%. Foot ulcers are preventable by adopting simple strategies thus reducing ulcers ending up in amputation. Fifteen percent of Diabetics develop foot ulcers during their life time with significant health related problems causing decrease in quality of life. It results in consumption of large healthcare resources. [1]

In the years between 1958 and 1993 the number of people diagnosed with diabetes multiplied five times. [2] In 1994, 135 million patients worldwide were living with diabetes mellitus. By 2025, it is

estimated would increase to 300 million. [3] Various scoring systems and classification of foot ulcers exists. Their intention is to compare the treatment modalities and outcome in different parts of the world. Different parameters are incorporated into these scoring systems such as ulcer depth, its site, presence or absence of infection, neuropathy and arterial insufficiency. All these scoring systems are complex and do not predict long term outcome in the patients. Diabetic Ulcer Severity Score addresses these shortcomings by being easy enough to be applied in day-to-day clinical practice. Categorizing diabetic foot ulcer as ulcer in the foot and ulcer in the toe is in itself a new method. Day to day clinical practice.

DUSS (Diabetic Ulcer Severity Score) is one of the latest wound-based system of classification which needs to be validated in our setup. [4]

As this scoring system also predicts amputation rates it will be a very useful tool for decision making in patients requiring amputations. [5]

Aims & Objectives

Aims: To evaluate Diabetic ulcer severity score in predicting the outcome in patients with Diabetic foot ulcer

Objectives: To study the progress of ulcer healing in diabetic patients to predict outcomes such as healing and amputation

Methodology

Total of 102 Diabetic patients with diabetic foot ulcers irrespective of their duration, admitted in the surgery department of ESICMC&H Kalaburgi were recruited into the study based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria mentioned below.

Ulcers were labelled infected if a purulent discharge was present with two of the local signs mentioned below. Wound depth was evaluated using a sterile blunt probe.

The ability to probe to bone with the presence of local inflammation (warmth, erythema, lymphangitis, lymphadenopathy, edema, pain) or signs of systemic infection and suggestive radiological features provided a clinical diagnosis of osteomyelitis. [6] Peripheral vascular disease was clinically detected by the absence of both pedal pulses, patients were categorized into groups having either single or multiple ulcerations on the same foot. Unhealed ulcers were followed up regularly. Once a patient's ulcer had healed completely either by primary healing or skin grafting or a lower-limb amputation performed, the outcome was noted.

Diabetic Ulcer Severity Score (DUSS): Ulcers were scored by the below mentioned variables. Diabetic Ulcer Severity Score (DUSS) was calculated by adding these separate scored variables to a theoretical maximum of 4.

Diabetic ulcer severity scoring system

Variables	Score 0	Score 1
Palpable Pedal pulses	Presence	Absence
Probing to bone	No	Yes
Ulcer site	Toes	Foot
Ulcer number	Single	Multiple

Ulcer grading depending on depth

Ulcer grades	Wound depth as measured by sterile blunt probe
Grade 1	Dermis
Grade 2	Subcutaneous tissue
Grade 3	Fascia
Grade 4	Muscle
Grade 5	Bone

Ulcer grading done to assess depth of ulcer to detect the presence of osteomyelitis.

Standard treatment care was given to all these patients, which included oral hypoglycemic or insulin for good control of Diabetes, health education, antibiotics and regular wound care. Healing was defined as complete epithelization or healing after skin grafting.

Amputation rate was defined as the percentage of patients undergoing either minor or major amputation within the observation period. Toe or forefoot amputations were taken as minor

amputation and below- or above-knee amputation were taken as major amputation.

The patients were regularly followed up.

Inclusion criteria:

1. Age limit >20yrs
2. All subjects suffering from Diabetes Mellites as per WHO criteria who have foot ulcers
 - Symptoms of Diabetes + random blood sugar > 200 mg/dl or
 - Fasting blood sugar > 126 mg/dl
 - 2-hour plasma glucose level > 200 mg/dl

3. All diabetic lower limb ulcers irrespective of ulcer duration

$$n \geq \frac{1.96 \times pq}{l^2}$$

Exclusion criteria:

1. Venous stasis ulcer with diabetes mellitus
2. Ulcers located above the ankle
3. Non diabetic foot ulcers
4. Non diabetic neuropathic ulcers
5. Loss of Follow up

According to Kummarkandath SA study

p=0.535

q = (1-p) = 0.465

Keeping l = 0.1

Then n is more than 95.53

Thus, the sample size of our study is 100.

Study design: A prospective Observational study.

Sample size: Based on the prevalence of diabetes and incidence of diabetic ulcer at ESICMC&H Kalaburgi, in the period of December-2023 to November -2024, approximate size of sample for the study is taken as 100.

Results

Age Distribution

Table 1: Age Distribution of the study participants

Distribution of age		
Age	N	%
<40	4	3.92%
41-50	22	21.57%
51-60	37	36.27%
61-70	30	29.41%
71-80	7	6.86%
>81	2	1.96%
Total	102	100.00%

In our study most common age group affected by Diabetic foot is 51-60 years followed by 61-70 years consisting of 36% and 29% respectively. Mean age of the study population is 58.373 years with a SD of 10.7987 and median age 58.5.

Table 2: Age Statistics of Study population

Age (years)	
Mean	58.373
Median	58.5
Mode	65
Minimum	34
Maximum	100
SD	10.7987

Sex Distribution

Table 3: Sex Distribution of Study population

Sex Distribution		
Sex	N	%
Male	76	74.51%
Female	26	25.49%
Total	102	100.00%

Most commonly affected by Diabetic foot in our study population were males with 74.51%.

DUSS Score Distribution

Table 4: DUSS Score Distribution

Score Distribution		
Score	N	%
1	15	14.71%
2	49	48.04%
3	20	19.61%
4	18	17.65%
Total	102	100.00%

In our study most ulcers were with DUSS Score of 2 followed by 3 with a mean score of 2.402 ± 0.946 and Median score of 2. Standard error of Mean is 0.0937.

Distribution of DUSS Score with Age: Majority of the Diabetic foot patients with DUSS Scores 1, 2, 3 and 4 are distributed among 51-60, 61-70, 51-60 and 71-80 years respectively. Distribution of DUSS Score with age is statistically significant with chi square 37.77 and p value of 0.001.

Table 5: Distribution of DUSS Score with Age

Age (years)	DUSS SCORE								Total	%
	1	%	2	%	3	%	4	%		
<40	0	0.00%	4	8.16%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	4	3.92%
41-50	5	33.33%	9	18.37%	6	30.00%	2	11.11%	22	21.57%
51-60	6	40.00%	16	32.65%	10	50.00%	5	27.78%	37	36.27%
61-70	4	26.67%	19	38.78%	3	15.00%	4	22.22%	30	29.41%
71-80	0	0.00%	1	2.04%	0	0.00%	6	33.33%	7	6.86%
>81	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	1	5.00%	1	5.56%	2	1.96%
Total	15	100.00%	49	100.00%	20	100.00%	18	100.00%	102	100.00%

The chi-square statistic is 37.777. The p-value is 0.001 The result is significant at $p < .05$

Distribution of DUSS Score with Sex: Diabetic foot patients with DUSS Scores 1, 2, 3 and 4 are distributed among Females and Males are 4, 13, 5,

4 and 11, 36, 15, 14 respectively. Distribution of DUSS Score with Sex is statistically insignificant with chi square of 0.143 and p value of 0.986.

Table 6: DUSS Score distribution with sex

Sex Distribution									
Sex	1	%	2	%	3	%	4	%	Total
Female	4	26.67%	13	26.53%	5	25%	4	22.22%	26
Male	11	73.33%	36	73.47%	15	75%	14	77.78%	76
Total	15	100%	49	100%	20	100%	18	100%	102

The chi-square statistic is 0.143. The p-value is .986. The result is not significant at $p < .05$.

Comparison of DUSS Score with Primary Treatment

In our study at presentation to our hospital, out of 15 patients with DUSS Score 1, all patients underwent debridement. Out of 49 patients with DUSS score 2: 28 and 21 patients underwent debridement and minor amputations respectively. Out of 20 patients with DUSS score 3: 17 and 3

patients underwent debridement and Minor amputation respectively as primary treatment.

Out of 18 patients with DUSS score 4: 14, 1 and 3 patient/s underwent debridement, Minor amputation and Major amputation respectively as primary treatment. The chi-square statistic is 39.439. The p-value is <0.000002 . The result is significant at $p < .05$

Table 7: Comparison of DUSS Score with Primary Treatment

DUSS Score vs 1st Treatment							
Score	Debridement	%	Minor Amputation	%	Major Amputation	%	Total
1	15	100.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	15
2	28	57.14%	21	42.86%	0	0.00%	49
3	17	85.00%	3	15.00%	0	0.00%	20
4	14	77.78%	1	5.56%	3	16.67%	18

The chi-square statistic is 31.439. The p-value is 0.0000209 The result is significant at $p < .05$

Comparison of DUSS Score with Final Treatment: In our study, out of 15 patients with DUSS Score 1, all patients ended up with need of debridement. Out of 49 patients with DUSS score 2: 19 and 30 patient ended up in debridement and minor amputation respectively. Out of 20 patients with DUSS score 3: 15, 4 and 1

patient/s ended up in debridement, Minor amputation and Major amputation respectively. Out of 18 patients with DUSS score 4: 4, 1 and 13 patient/s ended up in debridement, Minor amputation and Major amputation respectively. The chi-square statistic is 89.198. The p-value is <0.000001 . The result is significant at $p < .05$.

Table 8: Comparison of DUSS Score with Final treatment

Score Distribution								
Score	Debridement	%	Minor Amputation		Major Amputation	%	Total	%
1	15	100.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	15	100%
2	19	38.78%	30	61.22%	0	0.00%	49	100%
3	15	75.00%	4	20.00%	1	5.00%	20	100%
4	4	22.22%	1	5.56%	13	72.22%	18	100%

The chi-square statistic is 89.198. The p-value is <0.000001 The result is significant at p < .05

Comparison of DUSS Score with Diabetes Mellitus: 55 patients in our study were having diabetes for 1-5 years. 49 patients with Diabetes were having DUSS Score of 2.

Table 9: Comparison of DUSS Score with duration of DM

DUSS Score * DM Duration							
DUSS Score		DM in Years					Total
		1-5	6-10	11-15	16-20	>21	
1	10	5	0	0	0	15	
2	34	13	1	1	0	49	
3	10	7	2	0	1	20	
4	1	8	9	0	0	18	
Total	55	33	12	1	1	102	

Comparison of DUSS Score with Status of Wound at 2 Months: In our study, out of 15 patients with DUSS Score one, 14 were completely healed by the end of study period and 1 patient is healing. Among 49 patients with DUSS score two, 9 patients were yet to heal completely, 40 patients healed at the end of study

period. Among 20 patients with DUSS score three, 7 patients were yet to heal completely, 13 patients healed at the end of study period. Among 18 patients with DUSS score four, 1 patient is yet to heal completely and 17 patients healed at the end of study period.

Table 10: comparison of DUSS score with status of wound at 2 months

DUSS Score	N	Healing		Complete healed		total N
		%		N	%	
Score 1	1	5.56%		14	16.66%	15
Score 2	9	50.00%		40	47.61%	49
Score 3	7	38.89%		13	15.47%	20
Score 4	1	5.56%		17	20.23%	18
total	18	100.00%		84	100.00%	102

Comparison of DUSS Score with Outcome at Study End Point: In our study, out of 15 patients with DUSS Score one, 13 (86.67%) were completely healed by the end of study period and 1 (6.67%) healed with Skin grafting. None of the patient with DUSS score zero ended up in amputation. Among 49 patients with DUSS score two, 10 patients healed primarily and 26 patients underwent amputation (minor/major) at the end of study

period. Among 20 patients with DUSS score three, 2 patients healed primarily, 7 patients underwent skin grafting (grafting after amputations not included) and 4 underwent amputation at the end of study period. Among 18 patients with DUSS score four, 2 patients were healed primarily and 14 patients underwent amputation at the end of study period.

Table 11: comparison of DUSS score with outcome at study end point

Endpoint DUSS Score	Healing		Completely Healed primarily		Skin Grafting		Amputation		total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Score 1	1	6.67%	13	86.67%	1	6.67%	0	0.00%	15	100.00%
Score 2	9	18.37%	10	20.41%	4	8.16%	26	53.06%	49	100.00%
Score 3	7	35.00%	2	10.00%	7	35.00%	4	20.00%	20	100.00%
Score 4	1	5.56%	2	11.11%	1	5.56%	14	77.78%	18	100.00%

Table 12: Kaplan Meier Survival Analysis

Kaplan Meier Survival Analysis								
Means and Medians for Survival Time								
DUSS SCORE	Mean ^a				Median			
	Estimate	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval		Estimate	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Score 1	7.467	0.192	7.091	7.843	8.000	0.000	-	-
Score 2	7.878	0.048	7.784	7.971	8.000	-	-	-
Score 3	7.900	0.069	7.764	8.036	8.000	0.113	7.778	8.222
Score 4	7.846	0.116	7.620	8.073	-	-	-	-
Overall	7.816	0.044	7.728	7.903	8.000	0.102	7.800	8.200

a. Estimation is limited to the largest survival time if it is censored.

Estimated Mean healing time through Kaplan Meier survival analysis for DUSS Scores 1,2,3 and 4 are 7.467 weeks, 7.878 weeks, 7.9 weeks, 7.846 weeks respectively. Over all standard error of mean Healing time is 0.044.

Table 13: Cox Regression model

Overall Comparisons			
	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Log Rank (Mantel- Cox)	19.022	3	0.00027
Breslow (Generalized Wilcoxon)	18.067	3	0.00043
Tarone-Ware	18.611	3	0.00033

Test of equality of survival distributions for the different levels of DUSS SCORE.

ROC for DUSS Score in Major Amputations: DUSS Score cut-off for Major Amputations is 3. With sensitivity of 96% and specificity of 85%.

Table 14:

Area Under the Curve				
Test Result Variable(s)				
Area	Std. Error ^a	Asymptotic Sig. ^b	Asymptotic 95% Confidence Interval	
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
0.968	0.017	0.000	0.935	1.000

The test result variable(s): DUSS SCORE has at least one tie between the positive actual state group and the negative actual state group. Statistics may be biased.

a. Under the nonparametric assumption

b. Null hypothesis: true area = 0.5

Graph 1: Roc for DUSS Score in Major Amputations

Roc for DUSS Score in Minor Amputations: DUSS Score cut-off for Minor Amputations is 1.5. With sensitivity of 99% and specificity of 80%

Table 15:

Area Under the Curve				
Test Result Variable(s)				
Area	Std. Error ^a	Asymptotic Sig. ^b	Asymptotic 95% Confidence Interval	
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
0.385	0.054	0.066	0.280	0.490
The test result variable(s): DUSS SCORE has at least one tie between the positive actual state group and the negative actual state group. Statistics may be biased.				
a. Under the nonparametric assumption				
b. Null hypothesis: true area = 0.5				

Graph 2: Roc for Duss Score in Minor Amputations

Roc for Duss Score in Debridements: Duss Score cut-off for Debridement is ≥ 1 . With sensitivity of 99% and specificity of 99%

Table 16:

Area Under the Curve				
Test Result Variable(s)				
Area	Std. Error ^a	Asymptotic Sig. ^b	Asymptotic 95% Confidence Interval	
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
0.361	0.055	0.016	0.254	0.468
The test result variable(s): DUSS SCORE has at least one tie between the positive actual state group and the negative actual state group. Statistics may be biased.				
a. Under nonparametric assumption				
b. Null hypothesis: true area = 0.5				

Diagonal segments are produced by ties.

Graph 3: Roc for Duss Score in Debridements

Discussion

Most common age group affected in the study was between 51-60 years, mean age group was 58 years. Males are more commonly affected in the study accounting for 74.5% of all the cases. In the management of diabetic foot ulcers out of 102 patients 51.96 % underwent debridement, 33.4% underwent minor amputation and 13.7% underwent major amputations. In our study 14.71% patients presented with DUSS Score 1, 48.4% presented with DUSS score 2, 19.61% patients presented with DUSS score 3 and 17.6% presented with DUSS score 4.

The percentage patients with DUSS score 1 who were managed with debridement. And Minor amputation was 28.30% and 0% respectively. The percentage of patients with DUSS score 2 managed with debridement and minor amputation was 35.85 % and 90.91% respectively. The percentage of patients with DUSS score 3 who were managed by debridement, minor amputations and major amputations was 28.3%, 59.09 % and 7.14% respectively. The percentage of patients with DUSS score 4 managed by minor and major amputations was 1% and 92.8 % respectively In our study chances of healing is more

with DUSS score 1 and 2 and amputation rates are higher in DUSS score 3 and 4. In our study percentage of minor amputations was 33.5% and that of major amputations was 13.75% In the study by be chert et al patients with score of zero had no risk of major amputations and the patients with score of one had two point 4% risk of major amputations and those with a score of two heads seven 7% of major amputation and the patients with score of three had a risk of major amputation of about 11.2% and the patients with the score of four had 3.8% chances of major amputation In comparison to our present study none of the patients with score 01 and two had major amputation risk and 13% of the patients with score three had the risk of major amputation and 14% of the patients with score four had the risk of major amputation .in a study according to the Roc the DUSS score cut off for debridement is more than or equal to 1 with sensitivity of 99% and specificity of 99% and the DUSS score cut off four major amputation is more than or equal to three with sensitivity of 96% and specificity of 85%. According to a study undertaken in USA in 2004 through 2002 based on National Hospital discharge survey which evaluated 2.75 Lac patient records from 500 hospitals from 1996 onwards revealed

that elderly diabetics had twice the risk of developing a foot ulcer thrice the risk of developing a foot axis and four times the risk of developing osteomyelitis. Our study reveals that patients with longer duration of diabetes mellitus are more prone to develop foot ulcers and lesser the DUSS score more is the chance of ulcer healing and more is the DUSS score more is the chance of amputation of the limb and attendant complications

In our study on Kaplan Meier analysis the probability of need for Amputations with score 1 was 0%, 53% with score 2, 20% with score 3, 77% with score 4. In our study there was 100% probability of healing for score 0, decreasing to 25% with score 4 ($p=0.0002$), similar to as shown by the study conducted by Beckert et al. [7] They noted that a lower DUSS score was strongly associated with healing. Although the DUSS system makes no distinction between neuropathic and neuroischemic ulcers, there was a 93% probability of healing for uncomplicated ulcers (score 0), decreasing to 57% for ulcers with a severity score of 4 ($P=0.0001$) according to Kaplan Meier analysis.

Beckert et al [7] reported primarily healing of 74% ($n=1,000$), Prompers et al 77% ($n=1,229$), Oyibo et al 65% ($n=194$), Jeffcoate et al [8] 66% ($n=449$) and Gul et al 72% ($n=200$).

In the more than 10-year follow-up study conducted by Margolis et al a cohort of 24,616 individuals with a diabetic neuropathic foot ulcer treated within a multicenter wound care network were studied. Total of 1653 (6.7%) individuals had an amputation and 46.3% of these amputations were of a toe or ray (minor amputation). The percentage of those who had an amputation varied from 5.6% to 8.4%. Of those who had an amputation, the percentage that had a minor amputation increased over time from 4.0% in the earlier years to more than 60% in the later years of observation.

Conclusion

DUSS scoring system provides an easy diagnostic tool for predicting probability of healing or amputation by combining 4 clinically accessible wound-based parameters. Study groups can be stratified depending on the severity of the ulcers and thus helps in providing a simple streamlined approach in clinical setting without a need for any advanced investigation, but it does not alter the procedure of wound management.

Lower the DUSS score, higher are the chances of healing and higher the score higher is the chance of amputation. Maintaining good glycemic control, foot care, regular foot examinations are important

in detecting comorbid preulcerative callous which will help give us the best result of wound management

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